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Data Review

Data Citation

Anhelina Hrytsei (2025): 2020–2025 Aid Worker KIKA Incident Data (published on Insecurity Insight), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/C80669AE-BE7F-44B1-B2D0-753DEE7AC0DB>

Abstract

The 2020–2025 Aid Worker KIKA Incident Data is a publicly accessible dataset released by Insecurity Insight, a Geneva-based humanitarian organization that supports organisations, advocacy groups and researchers primarily through its research work. It contains information on incidents involving threats and violence against aid workers and aid agencies worldwide. The dataset is updated bi-weekly and shared on the Humanitarian Data Exchange (HDX) platform. Its main sources include reports from partner organizations and open-source information, such as social media and online media.

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Data Review: 2020–2025 Aid Worker KIKA Incident Data

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Methodological Foundation

The dataset's unit of analysis is a *KIKA incident*, defined as “an incident in which an aid worker was killed, injured, kidnapped, or arrested.” An *aid worker* is understood as “an employee, consultant, or volunteer attached to a not-for-profit humanitarian, multi-mandated, UN, or government aid agency.” This category may include, but is not limited to:

- Deminers
- Health workers affiliated with aid agencies
- Missionaries and staff of development agencies and local relief agencies
- UN staff
- Red Cross and Red Crescent staff and volunteers

The dataset contains more than 40 variables, which can be broadly grouped into the following categories:

- **Basic incident information:** Date; Country; Country ISO3 (country code); Admin 1 (incident location); Incident description.
- **Location:** Latitude; Longitude; Location of incident.
- **Actor:** Actor (type); Actor name.
- **Means of attack:** Weapon carried/used (arson; aerial bombing, missiles, or shelling; blunt instrument, dagger, knife, or machete; firearms; improvised explosive device; stones; unarmed; no information).
- **Consequences:**
 - a) *General:* Organisation affected (INGO; LNHO; NGO; Red Cross; UN agency); Program focus (demining; economic; education; health; human rights; hunger; protection; multiple; other; no information);
 - b) *Fatalities:* Aid workers killed; International aid workers killed; National aid workers killed; Male aid workers killed; Female aid workers killed;

- c) *Injuries*: Aid workers injured; International aid workers injured; Male aid workers injured; Female aid workers injured.
 - d) *Fatalities in captivity*: Aid workers killed in captivity; National aid workers killed in captivity; Male aid workers killed in captivity; Female aid workers killed in captivity;
 - e) *Kidnapping*: Aid workers kidnapped; Known kidnapping/arrest outcome; International aid workers kidnapped; National aid workers kidnapped; Male aid workers kidnapped; Female aid workers kidnapped;
 - f) *Arrest*: Aid workers arrested; International aid workers arrested; Male aid workers arrested; Female aid workers arrested;
- **SiND Incident ID** (incident number in the Security in Numbers Database).¹

The data are collected from two types of sources:

- Reports from partner organizations;
- Open sources, such as social media and online media.

The dataset is updated bi-weekly and shared on the Humanitarian Data Exchange (HDX) platform.²

Scope conditions

The dataset does not include incidents in which an aid worker was injured or died due to illness or an accident. It also does not provide information on perpetrators' intentions or the type of attack.

Additionally, the dataset does not focus specifically on attacks against healthcare workers unless they are affiliated with a relevant aid organization. It covers humanitarian aid personnel, whose roles may extend beyond medical assistance—for example, delivering aid or cleaning sites after armed attacks. Consequently, incidents involving medical personnel are lower than in datasets that cover healthcare more broadly.

Limitations

The dataset is neither representative nor a comprehensive record of all incidents in which an aid worker was killed, injured, kidnapped, or arrested. Its contents have also not been independently verified.

¹ Detailed description of each variable can be viewed in the dataset's codebook available at the link: <https://bit.ly/3g7QMNo>.

² "Aid Worker KKA (Killed, Kidnapped or Arrested) - Humanitarian Data Exchange," data.humdata.org, <https://data.humdata.org/dataset/sind-aid-worker-kka-dataset>.

Usage

The dataset includes information on 60 incidents that occurred in three post-Soviet countries between 2 January 2022 and 28 May 2025 (as of 2 December 2025), including:

- 58 incidents in Ukraine;
- 1 incident in Azerbaijan (Karabakh; 28 October 2020);
- 1 incident in Kyrgyzstan (First of May District; 2 January 2020).

All but one of the incidents in Ukraine were recorded after the start of the full-scale invasion in February 2022. Most incidents (50) occurred in oblasts experiencing active hostilities at the time—specifically Sumy, Donetsk, Luhansk, Kherson, and Zaporizhzhia oblasts. The remaining incidents were recorded in Lviv, Chernihiv, Zakarpattia, Vinnytsia, and the city of Kyiv.

25 incidents resulted in fatalities (all allegedly perpetrated by the Russian armed forces; six of those killed were foreign citizens). 40 incidents resulted in injuries (also all associated with the Russian armed forces; 11 of the injured were foreign citizens).

20 incidents involved INGOs and IRCC staff, two involved UN agencies, and 37—NGOs, LNGOs, and national Red Cross and Red Crescent societies employees and volunteers.

The dataset is topically similar to the Aid Worker Security Database (AWSD), which also covers “incidents involving violence against or the detention of aid workers in countries with a humanitarian presence.”³ However, it is more limited in scope: while AWSD provides data on incidents from 1997 to 2025, the KIKA dataset covers only 2020–2025. In addition, AWSD generally records more incidents (for example, from 1 January to 5 July 2022, AWSD recorded 231 incidents compared to 157 in the KIKA dataset). This discrepancy may result from several factors, including differences in access to sources, the rigor of analysis, and the interpretation of definitions. Nevertheless, the two datasets are comparable and can potentially be used for cross-checking and identifying missing data.

Funding

As of 2022, the Aid in Danger project was funded by the United States Agency for International Development (USAID). Following the Agency’s *de facto* dissolution in 2025, the project’s funding sources have not been updated on the organization’s official website.

³ Anhelina Hrytsei (2025): The Aid Worker Security Database (published on Humanitarian Outcomes), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/E7567B74-A162-47BC-9A41-3A87DAEF8FF3>.

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Note

This data review was produced by Anhelina Hrytsei, a Master's student in Peace and Conflict Studies at Uppsala University, as part of an Erasmus Traineeship at the Research Center for East European Studies at the University of Bremen.